

Analysis of The Effect of Convenience, Design, Trustworthiness, Price, & Various Food Choices on Customer Loyalty Through Perceived Value and Attitude Towards Food Delivery Apps On Grabfood Users In Surabaya

Gabriel Giani Oentoro, Amelia Amelia & Ronald Ronald

Abstract:

Indonesia is the most populous country in Southeast Asia, which makes it one of the countries with the largest market in Southeast Asia. In line with rapid technological advances, Indonesia has become an easy target for companies engaged in technology such as food delivery application service providers such as GrabFood. The findings of this study are expected to contribute to the advancement of science in the future, particularly in fields related to customer loyalty factors such as perceived value, various food choices, price, trustworthiness, design, and convenience, as evidenced by the varied attitudes toward food delivery apps. This study is a causal study, and the research technique is a quantitative method utilizing SPSS data processing. Data was gathered via questionnaires sent to 130 respondents based on specified characteristics, including men and women aged 18-60 years old residing in Surabaya who had used GrabFood at least twice in the previous six months and if they were currently using the GrabFood application.

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About Author (s)

Gabriel Giani Oentoro (corresponding author), Business School, University Pelita Harapan Surabaya Campus, Surabaya, Indonesia

Amelia Amelia, Business School, Universitas Pelita Harapan Surabaya Campus, Surabaya, Indonesia

Ronald Ronald, Business School, Universitas Pelita Harapan Surabaya Campus, Surabaya, Indonesia

1. Introduction

With the rapid development of technology, companies engaged in the service provider industry are also competing to reach more consumers, by providing applications in smart cellular phones that can provide various services that can provide consumers with whatever they want or need. Applications that provide various services can be referred to as "Super App". With Indonesia's position as the country with the largest population in Southeast Asia, it is not new if Indonesia is a place where many foreign companies enter and invest, especially companies that operate as application service providers or "Super Apps". The existence of the Covid-19 virus pandemic also affects the development and use of services from companies engaged in the "Super Apps", where the pandemic changes the way people carry out their activities so that it automatically changes the way most industries work, especially in the consumer goods industry such as food. where many people have switched from buying food conventionally or going to restaurants and buying food to using food delivery applications. that's when the "Super Apps" provider company provides food delivery services, one of the largest companies providing these services is Grabfood. GrabFood controls 53% of the food delivery service market share in Indonesia with a total market share of around US\$3.7 billion. Compared to other countries in southeast asia Furthermore, if you look at the projection of the growing food delivery industry with the message that by 2020 transportation and food delivery services can reach 5 billion USD and is projected to increase to 16 billion USD in 2025, it is not a it is not natural for food delivery service providers to compete for consumers in order to achieve maximum profit. In the high competition in the food delivery service provider industry, it is important for Grabfood to increase the Customer Loyalty of their customers in order to maintain their position as the holder of the highest market share in Indonesia. This study focuses on the influence of convenience, design, trustworthiness, price, various food choices on perceived value and then affects the attitude towards food delivery apps on Grabfood users in Surabaya.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Convenience

According to Collier & Kimes (2012) Convenience is defined as a time and effort expended to use an application until the last stage or in this context of purchase, it is also explained that the less time and effort expended the more convenient or convenient the use of an application, According to Jiang *et. al.*, (2013) Convenience is defined as an advantage that consumers get when shopping online where they can access their preferred shopping place anywhere and anytime and can make purchases, further explained that consumers can also order from places such as home or office. According to Cho *et. al.*, (2018) Convenience have a significant influence or effects on Perceived Value but rather less significant than the other variabel such as various food choices, design, trustworthiness. From these statements, we can make hypotheses that:

H1: Convenience has a strong positive impact on perceived value.

2.2 Design

According to Homburg *et. al.*, (2015) Design refers to a group of constitutive elements of a product that are seen and made by consumers as a multidimensional form that contains three dimensions, namely, aesthetic or beauty dimensions, functional dimensions and symbolic dimensions. According to Sreedhar (2016), application design is how well the design of an

application can fulfill the preferences desired by application users. According to Yang et. al., (2004), design represents the logical structure that comes from the application which includes also the understanding and operations required by the user to make it easy to use and understand it.

H2: Design has a considerable positive impact on perceived value.

2.3 Trustworthiness

According to Cho et. al (2018) Trustworthiness relates to the accuracy and ability of what restaurant partners and customers report, while according to Van Der Merwe & Puth (2014) Trustworthiness is an objective characteristic of a trustworthy party and makes it worthy to have that trust. According to Aw (2018), trust is a level of trust and competence that a person has in the integrity of the other party. Meanwhile, according to Song and Zahedi (2003), interpreting trust as a person's sincerity to be in a position that has vulnerability based on the expectations that other people have of other parties in that position.

H3: Perceived Value is positively influenced by trustworthiness.

2.4 Price

Friani et al., (2018) define price as the entire amount of money exchanged for a product or service. Tjiptono (2014) defines price as the amount of money in monetary units or other (non-monetary) features such as specific utilities or uses that are required to receive services. Sunyoto (2014) defines understanding price as the entire amount of money required to obtain a specific quantity of items, goods, or services. Price, according to Kotler and Armstrong (2012), is the amount of money customers pay for things or services, the total value of which they trade for the advantage of having or utilizing those items or services.

H4: Price has positive significant effect on Perceived Value

2.5 Various Food Choices

Product diversity, defined by Kotler and Keller (2012) as the range of items and goods supplied by a corporation and for sale by certain sellers, is product diversity. According to Engels (2015), product diversity refers to the range of items available, as well as their depth, breadth, and quality. Product variety, according to Dea et al. (2021), is a group of goods. The number of product lines, size options, color options, and other options are among the product lines and kinds available to purchasers. Product diversity, according to Karina et al., (2020), is the range of goods that may be interpreted if the product brand has product completeness, which includes changes in kind, brand, color, size, material, and quality.

H5: Perceived Value is positively influenced by a variety of food choices.

2.6 Perceived Value

Perceived value, according to Kotler and Keller (2012), is the difference between the customer's perception of advantages or benefits and all costs when compared to other alternatives. Furthermore, according to Kotler and Amstong (2016), perceived value is the customer's perception of the difference between all of the sales offer's advantages and costs in comparison to the rival offer. Perceived value, according to Aw (2018), is a consumer's total appraisal of the advantages of items consumed based on a comparison of pricing and benefits obtained. Perceived value, according to Wang et al. (2020), is a comprehensive estimate of the user's utility based on losses and advantages.

H6: Attitude Towards Food Delivery Apps is positively influenced by perceived value.

H7: Customer Loyalty is positively influenced by perceived value.

2.7 Attitude Towards Food Delivery Apps

According to Gaffari et. al., (2018) Attitude is an assessment, view and consumer interest in objects or objects that are relatively constant, According to Saifuddin Anwar (2013) attitude is defined as a pattern of behavior, inclination, accuracy, or predisposition to adapt oneself to social conditions or as an attitude to respond to conditioned social situations. According to Jihad & Haris (2012) attitude is defined as a sense of liking or disliking related to the response shown by a person to a particular object. According to Al Amin et. al., (2020) mobile food delivering apps is an application system where customers can order food via cellular with available applications. According to Ray et., al (2019), online food delivery services refer to internet-based services where customers can order food and deliver food to their homes at any time. As a comparison, food delivering apps work through mobile apps. According to Xiao & Dong (2015) delivering food apps makes it easier for consumers to find and order the food they want online.

H8: Customer Loyalty is positively influenced by customer attitudes toward food delivery apps.

2.8 Customer Loyalty

According to Amin (2016), customer loyalty is the intention of consumers to revisit products and services consistently in the future, and also provide positive recommendations to others regarding these services or products. In the world of online banking, Anderson and Srinivasan (2003) define customer loyalty as a form of consumer tendency to continue to use certain websites, visit them frequently, and show high site adhesion with high retention times. According to Deng et al., (2010); Lin and Wang, (2006); Teng and Chen, (2014). Loyalty is also defined as the intention to repeatedly use certain products, services or information technology, besides that loyalty is also used interchangeably with continuance intention (eg, Liao et al, 2016). competitive against competitors. According to Bowen and Shoemaker (1998) refers to the possibility of a consumer to return to an organization and their willingness to become partners to the organization.

3. Hypothesis

The goal of this paper is to check and examine the effect of Convenience, Design, Trustworthiness, Price, Various Food Choices, to Customer Loyalty through Attitude Towards Food Delivery Apps and Perceived Value of Grabfood user in Surabaya. Thus the following hypotheses are used

H1: Convenience has a strong positive impact on perceived value.

H2: Design has a considerable positive impact on perceived value.

H3: Perceived Value is positively influenced by trustworthiness.

H4: Price has positive significant effect on Perceived Value

H5: Perceived Value is positively influenced by a variety of food choices.

H6: Attitude Towards Food Delivery Apps is positively influenced by perceived value.

H7: Customer Loyalty is positively influenced by perceived value.

H8: Customer Loyalty is positively influenced by customer attitudes toward food delivery apps.

4. Method

The research method used in this study is a quantitative research method. The sampling method in this study uses a non-probabilty sampling technique which is carried out with a questionnaire as a research instrument or a tool in data collection, where respondents will assist researchers in collecting data through questionnaires. In this study, 130 respondents were collected who answered the questionnaire given, while the research model can be seen below.

Figure 1. Research Model

Source: Cho *et. al.*, 2018

5. Result

Multiple Regression was utilized to evaluate the relationships between the variables in this investigation. SPSS 22.0 was utilized as a statistical analysis tool to address the study challenge. The next stage is to undertake descriptive statistic analysis when the surveys have been returned. Table 1 demonstrates that men are more likely than women to fill out surveys, as seen by the fact that out of 130 respondents, 77 (59.2%) of those who use Grabfood are men and 53 (40.8%) are women. This implies that Grabfood users are predominantly male.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	77	59,2	59,2	59,2
	Female	53	40,8	40,8	100.0
	Total	130	100.0	100.0	

Source: own calculation

Table 2 shows that the characteristics of respondents based on age are dominated by the age group 18-35, which accounts for 121 respondents (93,1 percent). The 36-50 age group comes in second with 9 replies (6,9 percent). And there were no responders in the 50-60 age range (0,0 percent). This indicates that the majority of responders belong to the generation X and Y age groups.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	18 - 35 years	121	93,1	93,1	93,1
	35 - 50 years	9	6,9	6,9	100
	50 - 60 years	0	0	0	
	Total	130	100.0	100.0	

Source: own calculation

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
C1	130	4,077	,8128
C2	130	4,323	,7994
C3	130	4,300	,9372
C	130	4,2333	,67137
D1	130	4,215	,8444
D2	130	4,238	,8146
D3	130	4,208	,9293
D	130	4,2205	,80326
T1	130	4,354	,7662
T2	130	4,277	,7777
T3	130	4,138	,8422
T	130	4,2564	,68895
P1	130	3,608	,9523
P2	130	3,615	1,0068
P3	130	3,731	,9216
P	130	3,6513	,87738
VF1	130	4,238	,8146
VF2	130	4,362	,8260
VF3	130	4,331	,8202
VF	130	4,3103	,75305

PV1	130	3,577	1,0845
PV2	130	3,969	,9313
PV3	130	3,731	,9628
PV	130	3,7590	,83425
ATF1	130	4,115	,7937
ATF2	130	4,085	,8263
ATF3	130	3,931	,8995
ATF	130	4,0436	,73005
CL1	130	4,215	,7873
CL2	130	4,092	,7919
CL3	130	3,962	,9184
CL	130	4,0897	,75829
Valid N (listwise)	130		

Source: own calculation

Table 3 reveals that the average score of the mean for the overall indicator is more than 3.61, indicating that all variables' indicators are considered as agreeable by all respondents. Furthermore, if the standard deviation is less than 2.0, the responses supplied by respondents are homogeneous. Various Food Choices had the highest mean average of 4.3103. This might mean that respondents agree more with the indicators of Various Food Choices than with the indicators of other factors. Price has the largest standard deviation score, which is .87738. This might suggest that respondents' responses to Price are the least homogenous when compared to other factors.

5.1.1 Validity Test

The statements are deemed legitimate if the factor loading value is greater than 0.172. Because the factor loading for each indicator is more than 0,172, all indicators utilized to estimate each variable are valid based on the best of the data validity.

In d.	FL	In d.	FL	Ind.	FL	In d.	FL	Ind	FL	Ind	FL	Ind.	FL	Ind	FL
Convenience		Design		Trustworthiness		Price		Various Food Choices		Perceived Value		Attitudes Towards Food Delivery Apps		Customer Loyalty	
C1	,356	D1	,855	T1	,740	P1	,769	VF1	,782	PV1	,642	ATF1	,691	CL1	,757
C2	,653	D2	,857	T2	,716	P2	,822	VF2	,841	PV2	,695	ATF2	,763	CL2	,842
C3	,552	D3	,817	T3	,628	P3	,821	VF3	,818	PV3	,564	ATF3	,650	CL3	,791

Source: own calculation

5.1.1 Reliability Test

The cronbach's alpha value is compared to the statement's reliability, and if the value is more than 0.6, the statement is deemed reliable.

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items
Convenience	,696
Design	,924
Trustworthiness	,835
Price	,901
Various Food Choices	,907
Perceived Value	,791
Attitude Towards Food Delivery Apps	,839
Customer Loyalty	,897
Source: own calculation	

Table 5 shows that the Cronbach alpha value for the variables of Convenience, Design, Trustworthiness, Price, Various Food Choices, Perceived Value, Attitude Towards Food Delivery Apps, and Customer Loyalty is more than 0.60. As a result, it may be argued that the statements describing the variables are consistent and dependable, and that they can be utilized for further investigation.

5.1.3 Results of Multiple Regression

1. Convenience, Design, Trustworthiness, Price, Various Food Choices to Perceived Value

The results of multiple regression are as follows:

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	-,682	,291		-2,339	,021
	C	,099	,090	,079	1,094	,276
	D	,218	,068	,210	3,203	,002
	T	,139	,092	,115	1,514	,133
	P	,317	,063	,333	5,049	,000
	VF	,314	,084	,284	3,762	,000
a. Dependent Variable: PV						
Source: own calculation						

From table 6, the regression equation can be written as follows:

$$PV = b_1.C + b_2.D + b_3.T + b_4.P + b_5.VF$$

$$PV = 0,079.C + 0,210.D + 0,115.T + 0,333.P + 0,284.VF$$

According to table 6, all of the independent variables have a positive impact on Perceived Value. Price has the highest regression coefficient (0.333) when compared to the other factors. As a result, Price has the greatest effect on Perceived Value. Convenience, on the other hand, has the smallest impact on Perceived Value (0.079).

2. Perceived Value, Attitude Towards Food Delivery Apps to Customer Loyalty

The result of multiple regression are as follows:

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
3	(Constant)	1,028	,265		3,884	,000
	C	,209	,079	,230	2,658	,009
	D	,563	,090	,542	6,268	,000
a. Dependent Variable: CL						
Source: own calculation						

From the table 7, the regression equation can be written as follows:

$$CL = b7.PV + b8.ATF$$

$$CL = 0,230.PV + 0,542.ATF$$

Table 6 shows that all of the independent factors have a favorable impact on Customer Loyalty. With a regression value of 0,542, Attitude Towards Food Delivery Apps has the highest regression coefficient of all the variables. As a result, Attitude Towards Food Delivery Apps has a significant impact on customer loyalty. Then comes Perceived Value, which has a value of 0.230.

5.1.4 Results of Simple Regression

1. Perceived Value to Attitude Towards Food Delivery Apps

The results of simple regression are as follows:

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
2	(Constant)	1,726	,211		8,167	,000
	PV	,617	,055	,705	11,237	,000
a. Dependent Variable: ATF						
Source: own calculation						

From table 8, the regression equation can be written as follows:

$$ATF = b6.PV$$

$$ATF = 0,705.PV$$

The independent variable has a positive impact on Attitude Towards Food Delivery Apps, according to table 8. With a regression coefficient of 0,705, Perceived Value has the highest correlation. As a result, Perceived Value influences Attitude Towards Food Delivery Apps.

5.1.5 F-test

According to SPSS calculations, the significance of F test values in model 1, model 2, and model 3 are all 0.000, indicating that all five independent factors collectively have a substantial impact on the dependent variable.

Model		Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	63,254	5	12,651	59,136
	Residual	26,527	124	,214	
	Total	89,781	129		
a. Dependent Variable: PV					
b. Predictors: (Constant), C, D, T, P, VF					
Source: own calculation					

	Model	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	34,143	1	34,143	126,271
	Residual	34,610	128	,270	
	Total	68,753	129		
a. Dependent Variable: ATF					
b. Predictors: (Constant), PV					
Source: own calculation					

	Model	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	38,727	2	19,364	69,374
	Residual	35,448	127	,279	
	Total	74,175	129		
a. Dependent Variable: CL					
b. Predictors: (Constant), PV, ATF					
Source: own calculation					

5.1.6 t-test

1. Perceived Value: Convenience, Design, Trustworthiness, Price, and a Variety of Food Options
The t test was performed to see if the independent factors of Convenience, Design, Trustworthiness, Price, and Various Food Choices to Perceived Value have a significant impact on Perceived Value partly (independently). If the t test result is less than 0.05, the variable is said to be significantly impacted by partly.

2. Attitude Towards Food Delivery Apps and Perceived Value

The t test was conducted to see if the independent variables Perceived Value and Attitude Towards Food Delivery Apps had any effect on Perceived Value (independently). If the t test result is less than 0.05, the variable is said to be significantly impacted by partly.

3. Customer Loyalty, Perceived Value, and Attitude Towards Food Delivery Apps

The t test was performed to see if the independent variables of Perceived Value, Attitude Towards Food Delivery Apps, and Customer Loyalty have a partial (independent) impact on Perceived Value. If the t test result is less than 0.05, the variable is said to be significantly impacted by partly.

5.1.7 Final Result

The findings from this study indicate that in general there are 6 supported hypotheses and 2 rejected hypotheses, while the variable that has the greatest influence on consumers to have Customer Loyalty for Grabfood products and services is the Price variable, followed by Various Food Choices, Design and then Trustworthiness, Convenience variable which has a positive effect but has no significant effect on the formation of Customer Loyalty.

The first hypothesis stated that Convenience has a significant effect on Perceived Value is not supported. The rejection of this hypothesis can be seen in the results of the t test where the significance value is 0.276 (above 0.05) which indicates that the hypothesis is rejected. This insignificant hypothesis is supported by research from Srivastastavaa & Kaulb (2014) where it is explained that Convenience does not have a significant direct influence on Perceived Value,

this is because in this study it was found that the research had a mediating variable, namely Customer Experience which showed that customer experience fully mediates relationship between the two antecedents.

The second hypothesis stated that Design has a significant effect on Perceived Value. This hypothesis is accepted and supported by the results of the t test where the significance value is 0.002 (below 0.05) which indicates that the hypothesis is accepted. This significant hypothesis is supported by research from Cobelli et al., (2018) which explains that ease of use (design) or variables related to display pages on platforms are easy to read, text, labels and menus on platforms are easy to understand and respondents get platforms. easy to use shows a significant effect on perceived value.

The third hypothesis stated that Trustworthiness has a significant effect on Perceived Value. This hypothesis is not supported and can be proven by the results of the t test where the significance value is 0.133 (above 0.05) which indicates that the hypothesis is rejected. The insignificant hypothesis does not support previous research by Cho et al., (2018), in which the trustworthiness variable is the most influential variable on perceived value, then this hypothesis has no effect. This hypothesis is supported by research from Hashim et al., (2015) where it is explained that trust does not have a significant effect on the perceived value of students in Malaysia. This is because it is suspected that there are other variables that can have a greater influence on perceived value such as satisfaction, quality of service and other facilities that can be provided.

The fourth hypothesis stated that Price has a significant effect on Perceived Value. This hypothesis is supported by the results of the t test where the significance value is 0.000 (below 0.05) which indicates that the hypothesis is accepted. This significant hypothesis is supported by research from Konuk (2019) which explains that price fairness has a positive and significant effect on consumers of organic restaurants in Istanbul, Turkey. In this study, it was found that the price determined by the restaurant should not only look at the benefits that can be obtained but also from the consumer's view of the price offered, if the price is considered fair it can increase the perception of value from consumers.

The fifth hypothesis stated that Various Food Choices have a significant effect on Perceived Value. This hypothesis is supported by the results of the t test where the significance value is 0.000 (below 0.05) which indicates that the hypothesis is accepted. This significant hypothesis is supported by research from Azizul et al., (2019) which explains that various food choices have a significant effect on customer perceived value for food delivery apps consumers, who are young people who work in Shah Alam, Malaysia where consumers want food delivery apps in order to be able to access food delivery apps. provide a choice of food and restaurants that can be chosen easily and can provide clear information for consumers.

The sixth hypothesis is that Perceived Value has a significant effect on Attitudes Towards Food Delivery Apps. This hypothesis is supported by the results of the t test where the significance value is 0.000 (below 0.05) which indicates that the hypothesis is accepted. This significant hypothesis is supported by research from Hsu et al., (2016) which explains that perceived value which is divided into hedonic value and utilitarian value has a positive and significant effect on attitudes and satisfaction of consumers which then affects stickiness or the nature of consumers' attachment to an application.

The seventh hypothesis states that Perceived Value has a significant effect on Customer Loyalty. This hypothesis is supported by the results of the t test where the significance value is 0.000 (below 0.05) which indicates that the hypothesis is accepted. This significant hypothesis is also supported by research from Rasheed et al., (2014) which explains that perceived value affects customer loyalty, where if service quality is increased it will result in increased consumer perceived value which in turn affects customer loyalty.

The eighth hypothesis states that Attitude Towards Food Delivery Apps has a significant effect on Customer Loyalty. This hypothesis is supported by the results of the t test where the significance value is 0.000 (below 0.05) which indicates that the hypothesis is accepted. This significant hypothesis is also supported by research from Smith (2020) which explains that attitude towards brand has a positive and significant effect on the emergence of customer loyalty, in this study it is explained that customer loyalty can be achieved when consumers feel satisfied (customer satisfaction) and when a good attitude appears. from the consumer (attitude towards the brand) to the service provider brand.

6. Discussion

The purpose of this research was to discover the elements that impact the establishment of customer loyalty among Grabfood consumers in Surabaya. Convenience, Design, Trustworthiness, Price, and Various Food Choices all have positive and substantial influences on Perceived Value, according to this study model. Furthermore, Perceived Value has a positive and substantial impact on Attitude Towards Food Delivery Apps, and both Perceived Value and Attitude Towards Food Delivery Apps have a favorable and significant impact on Customer Loyalty. As a result, six of the eight hypotheses suggested are supported, while two hypotheses are rejected. Variables such as Attitude Towards Food Delivery Apps, Perceived Value, Price, Various Food Choices, and Design have been identified as crucial elements to notice based on the research findings, since these variables have a significant impact on customer loyalty among Grabfood users in Surabaya. According to the findings of the study, convenience, design, trustworthiness, price, and a variety of food options are all factors that should be addressed in order to entice users to use Grabfood services. As a result, the management implications should be more concentrated on these factors. Based on the theory that has been constructed, the following management implications of these findings may be made: First, two factors, Perceived Value and Attitude Towards Food Delivery Apps, combine to generate the Customer Loyalty variable. The Attitude Towards Food Delivery Apps variable is ranked top as a variable with a substantial influence on customer loyalty, indicating that Grabfood customers will have a loyal or loyal attitude to use the Grabfood service application if they have a positive attitude or behavior toward it. When consumers use Grabfood, they believe it is useful; consumers are very supportive of ordering food through Grabfood; consumers want to use Grabfood when they buy food; and "I want to use Grabfood when I'm going to buy food" is one of the indicators of Attitude Towards Food Delivery Apps with the lowest score. This signal might be enhanced by sending smartphone alerts to Grabfood customers during times when they are most likely to eat or drink, such as notifications of dishes that are ordered at specific times, such as Nasi Pecel. The moonlight in the morning, Nasi Padang throughout the day, and the sunrise in the evening. Second, the perceived value variable influences customers' attitudes about food delivery apps, indicating that if consumers' perceived value or evaluation of the Grabfood app is positive, they will have a positive attitude or behavior toward the app. Consumers may believe that they are getting better food or beverage goods for the price given, that purchasing things through Grabfood is a worthwhile use of their time, and that ordering products through Grabfood is better than buying food traditionally. "Compared to buying traditional food, it is

preferable to utilize Grabfood," is one of the Perceived Value indicators with the lowest score. This indication may be improved by giving information on whether or not drivers and staff of restaurants that pack food have been vaccinated. Third, Convenience, Design, Trustworthiness, Price, and Various Food Choices factors combine to generate Perceived Value variables. Where Price is the most influential variable in Perceived Value, it suggests that consumers from Grabfood in Surabaya would have a higher assessment or perception if they can pick food goods that are comparable with the price supplied, and if they can receive food products at affordable costs. "When I order food through Grabfood, the food is commensurate with the price offered" is one of the Price indicators with the lowest value, which can be improved by providing a rating feature to consumers, namely by providing a kind of survey to consumers with the question "is the food you buy worth it?" or the option to fill in your own excuses why it isn't worth it, but with the added option of a commensurate price option for the food that has been ordered. To make this function work, the price specified must be close to the manufacturer's approximate pricing. Fourth, Various Food Choices variables occupy the second position as variables that have a major influence on Perceived Value because as a consumer, you definitely want to get choices from various interesting restaurants, get offers of various choices of varied food and can order food at various prices through Grabfood. One of the indicators of Various Food Choices that has the lowest score is "Grabfood offers a variety of interesting restaurant choices" and can be increased by

Fifth, Design variables occupy the third position as variables that have a major influence on Perceived Value because as consumers, they definitely want to experience an application design structure that is easy to follow, an application design that is easy to understand, and also an application design that makes it easy for users to read all the terms and conditions. One of the Design indicators that has the lowest value is "The design of the Grabfood application makes it easy for me to read all terms and conditions (for example, payment, warranty" and can be improved by using the "add a promo" feature if you want to pay for an order Grabfood can provide a filter to the customer). promos that can be used, cannot be used and cannot be used to make it easier for consumers to choose promos and to further clarify which promos can be used by consumers and which cannot. Sixth, Trustworthiness variables occupy the fourth position as variables that affect the Perceived Value variable but have no significant effect, this is because although consumers certainly want to feel safe when making payments through Grabfood, feel safe when ordering food through Grabfood, and get reliable information. However, because the majority of consumers from Grabfood are generations of X, Y, and Z who have understood the working system of the application and because similar features exist in other services such as Grabfood, it is not a significant factor. One of the indicators of Trustworthiness that has the lowest value is "The information provided by Grabfood is trustworthy" and can be improved by requiring product manufacturers to fill in the photos of the products they enter into Grabfood and provide information about the basic ingredients contained in the product then from Grabfood can form a team to check at the point of sale whether the photos and products are appropriate.

Seventh, Convenience variables occupy the fifth position on the variables that have an influence on the Perceived Value variable but have no significant effect where even though consumers want to feel the orders they ordered reach their hands according to the time estimated on the application, it allows consumers to order food or beverage products at any time. , as well as allowing consumers to order food or beverage products anywhere, but because the majority of

Grabfood consumers or respondents from the research are a group that is classified as young and coupled with the many applications that offer the same service, namely the convenience that consumers get and feel from application services such as Grabfood. This makes the service as usual and if Grab cannot fulfill the service then there is a similar application substitution. This causes the convenience variable to have no significant effect. One of the Convenience indicators that has the lowest score is "Grabfood delivers my order according to the estimated time" and can be improved by providing features on the Grabfood driver application to provide the fastest route to deliver products to consumers, and providing training to drivers regarding the location of consumer housing as well as the fastest route to reach that location from where to buy products wherever they are located. Or give rewards to drivers for completing orders on time.

Research Limitation

Given the limitations of the research object, which only takes respondents, namely users of Grabfood services in Surabaya, it is hoped that the next study will use the same model or be modified so that it can be applied to a variety of objects in order to obtain more general results on the factors that influence customer loyalty. Then it's important to keep in mind that the results don't always represent all Grabfood users. It is believed that future research will be able to supplement the current variables in this study, such as adding the Customer Satisfaction variable or other variables, to improve knowledge of the elements that drive Customer Loyalty.

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